

Start Survey - AWT

Start of Block: Default Question Block

Q2 I appreciate your interest in this research! This survey will provide information about what it entails to participate in this research. **Content of this Qualtrics Survey:** Information letter Informed consent Brief descriptives Instructions to install the app A link to a SURFfilesender to safely download the app If you have any questions or comments, feel free to contact the executive researcher, **name of researcher redacted for reviewing purposes**

check This research will focus on scientific staff, so please confirm whether you are a scientific staff member before proceeding with the survey.

- I am part of scientific staff (lecturer, researcher, PhD-candidate, post-doc assistant/associate/full professor)
- I am not part of scientific staff

End of Block: Default Question Block

Start of Block: Explanation scientific sample

Q15 We appreciate your interest in this research. For our initial exploration of measuring work characteristics using Active Window Tracking data, we will focus on a sample of scientific personnel. Unfortunately, you won't be able to join the research at this stage. You can still test the application which stores the AWT data on your computer, allowing you to explore your digital activity yourself. On the following pages, you'll find instructions on how to download and install. We may later be interested in broadening our sample and would appreciate your participation at that time. If you have any questions, don't hesitate to contact **Name + email**

End of Block: Explanation scientific sample

Start of Block: Information letter

Q4 Information Letter

racking the Digital Workday **Researchers** Lead researcher (PhD-candidate):*redacted* Daily supervisor: *redacted* Supervisors: *redacted* This study has been reviewed and approved by the Ethics Review Board (on

19 September 2025).

What is the purpose of this study? This study investigates how work characteristics can be measured using Active Window Tracking (AWT) data and how these characteristics relate to well-being outcomes such as work engagement and exhaustion. A digital tool can be installed on a computer that allows for Active Window Tracking. This tool will track which application and window title is active at any given time and save it locally (on the computer). Based on this data, we aim to explore the extent to which work characteristics, such as workload and work variety, can be derived. What will I do if I choose to be in this study? Participation involves installing a tool for AWT, which tracks your computer activity locally. We ask that you monitor your computer activity for at least 25 working days using this app. During this period, you will receive short daily and weekly surveys (approximately 3 minutes each), as well as a one-time survey collecting demographic information at the start of the research (which you are filling in now). These surveys will be sent to you via email. To make it easier to fill in, the surveys can also be sent to you via Signal, but that is optional. The AWT data and survey responses will be linked using a pseudonymized code to protect your privacy. Only the lead researcher (Mari Braakman) will have access to the key linking participants to their pseudonymized codes. After the data collection period, we will ask you to export and share the AWT data with the research group. If you are interested, we can provide you with preliminary results of your computer activity. How long will I be in the study? Participation can start at any time up until March 9 and will continue for a period of five weeks. Missing days within the five weeks (e.g., due to days off) are not a problem. What are the possible risks or discomforts? Because AWT data reflects your computer activity, it may feel personal or privacy-sensitive. To protect your privacy, all data will be stored locally on your computer during the data collection period. After the first month, you may choose to export the data and securely share it with the research team via SURFfilesender. Once shared, the data will be securely stored on *redacted*'s servers and will only be accessible to the research team. No information that would lead back to you will be shared with others. Are there any potential benefits? Participating in this study may provide you with valuable insights into your work patterns and potential areas for improvement. After analyzing your data, we can offer feedback in the form of a meeting or a personalized report, highlighting notable patterns in your computer activity. Do I have control over which data will be shared? Before sharing your data, you will have the opportunity to review it yourself. The application stores your activity locally, and when exported, it will create a CSV file on your computer, which can be opened with common software (such as Excel). You may delete, pseudonymize, or filter out any entries, time periods, or window titles that you do not wish to share. Only after this review do you provide the data to the research team. Because it may be difficult to apply the right filters in the dataset, we offer the option to schedule a short meeting with *name redacted*. In this meeting, you can get help applying filters yourself or discuss how we can safely make the necessary changes together, ensuring that no sensitive data is shared. Will information about me and my participation be kept confidential? Your responses will be kept strictly confidential, and digital data will be stored in secure computer files on the servers of *redacted*. Any publications based on this research will not include your name or any other individual information by which you could be identified. The project's research records may be reviewed by departments at *redacted* responsible for regulatory and research oversight and stored and encrypted for a period of 10 years, in accordance with *redacted*'s research policy. What are

my rights if I take part in this study? Your participation in this study is voluntary. You may choose not to participate or, if you agree to participate, you can withdraw your participation at any time without any negative consequences. Who can I contact if I have questions about the study? If you have questions, comments, or concerns about this research project, you can talk to one of the researchers. Please contact *redacted* or *redacted* If you have questions about your rights while taking part in the study or have concerns about the treatment of research participants, please write to: the secretary of the *redacted* If you have any questions or concerns about the way *redacted* handles your personal data in this research, please send an e-mail to *redacted*, the Faculty of Science Privacy Officer, through *redacted*

End of Block: Information letter

Start of Block: Informed consent

Q7 Informed Consent I have been invited to take part in the study, *Tracking the Digital Workday*. I have received and read the information letter about the study. I have had the opportunity to ask questions, and all my questions have been answered to my satisfaction. My participation is entirely voluntary. I am free to decline or withdraw from the study at any point, without giving a reason and without experiencing any negative consequences. I give permission for the research team to collect and process my data as described in the information letter. The data will be pseudonymized and securely stored on the servers of *redacted*. I also agree to the research team storing the data for a period of ten years in line with the university's data management guidelines. If you have read the information and agree to participate, please fill in your email address below. A pseudonymized code and a link to the daily surveys will be sent to you by *name redacted* In the following pages, instructions are provided for downloading and installing the application, which stores Active Window Tracking Data locally on your computer. It is possible to test the application before agreeing to participate. Don't hesitate to contact *name redacted* for any questions you might have about the application or your participation in this research.

email If you agree to participate, please fill in your email address below.

End of Block: Informed consent

Start of Block: Block 6

Report Do you wish to receive a personalized report about your data after the study is complete? (answer can be changed later in the process)

- Yes, I want to receive a personalized report
 - No, I don't want to receive a personalized report
-

Tel If you want to receive the daily and weekly surveys via Signal, please fill in your telephone number below (optional).

Survey_time At what time would you prefer to receive your daily survey?

- 16:00
- 16:30
- 17:00
- 17:30
- 18:00
- 18:30
- 19:00

End of Block: Block 6

Start of Block: Demographics

Hours How many hours do you work per week according to your contract?

Q23 Are there any fixed days or parts of days on which you do not work? For example, part-time staff might always have Wednesday off, or Wednesday and Friday afternoons. If not, leave this box empty.

Faculty What academic field or domain do you primarily work in?

- Geosciences
- Humanities
- Law, Economics and Governance
- Medical Science
- STEM
- Social and Behavioural Sciences
- Veterinary Medicine

Uni Which university do you (primarily) work at?

Function What is your function/position?

- Lecturer
- Researcher
- PhD-candidate
- Post-doc
- Assistant professor
- Associate professor
- Full professor
- Other

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: Instructions for downloading and installing

Q16 Below you can find the link to the SURFfilesender link, where you can download the app and the installation instructions. Please follow the instructions for your platform (macOS, Windows, or Linux) carefully. Do you need any help? Please contact *name redacted* . Please click here for the installation instructions and the zip files to install the application.Or copy the following link into your browser: *expired link*

End of Block: Instructions for downloading and installing
